

The project in a nutshell

Science and demographic data suggest that soon 10% of the population born in Europe will result from assisted reproduction techniques (ART). About half of people that wish to have children will go to specialized centers. Therefore, Assisted Reproduction Technology (ART) plays a significant role in the reproductive health of European society and is a fast-growing part of the health industry.

Surprisingly, nobody has worried about how young people understand, react to, and interact with Reproduction technologies. Human reproduction is presented as a privileged confluence between science, industry, government, and citizens. In this context, **"B²-InF - Giving voice to citizens towards improving Assisted Reproduction Technologies for Society"** will help understand the evolution of reproductive science and society to promote proactive and anticipatory policymaking, align research developments with the needs, expectations, and values of society.

The B²-InF project is the first project of its kind. There are in Europe many studies on Assisted Reproductive Technologies (ART); however, they mainly focus on the experiences of patients or on medical practices and the issues they raised. Very few studies explore ART knowledge and representations in the general population, i.e., in ART non-users and people who are not, a priori, infertile.

We know even less among young adults. Do they know fertility problems? The existing techniques to overcome these problems? The law and policies that regulate these techniques in their country? What do they think about it? Would they be disposed to use ART? What are their expectations in this respect? These are all questions that the project addresses. The other component of the highly innovative project is the analysis of the offers made by the clinics, primarily through their advertising (Websites, flyers, etc.). Do they generally target a particular audience? What techniques do they offer? How do they explain infertility and represent parenthood?

In other words, B²-InF will seek to answer two questions:

- 1. How do young people perceive and think about ART?**
- 2. How can ART clinics better align their research, services, and information with the views, concerns and expectations of citizens?**

By answering these questions, B²-InF aims to promote public participation in the science and provision of ART so that these become more responsive to the needs and concerns of society.

The Consortium will carry out the project in three stages. In the first stage, we collect data about perceptions and awareness of ART in young populations and the information offered by clinics to their clients through several structured interviews. In the second stage, this data is analyzed from sociocultural, legal, and gender perspectives to detect misalignments and other weak points and determine ways to improve the information offered by clinics. The third stage will focus on the dissemination of the findings.

The main result that the B²-InF consortium would like to achieve is the development of national and international guides with concrete and practical guidelines to significantly improve ART for the European society of tomorrow.